

A new food product from solanum lycocarpum

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Abstract— *The wolf apple is otherwise known as fruit of wolf. It is grown in small brushes or small branched tree. It is perennial. It belongs to the family of tomato, but it is wild species. Now-a-days most of the people are suffer by diabetes, heart problem, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, blood pressure,obesity due to high cholesterol in our body.The overall raised cholesterol is estimated to cause 2.6 million death and 29.7 million people cannot lead their normal life.Not only it control cholesterol but also it contains many medicine benefits,like resist slash and burn.The main advantage it is grown in dry and arid conditions.So it is grown where the cultivation is less due to irrigation.*

Index Terms— *wolf apple; butter; diabetes; obesity; cholesterol*

I. INTRODUCTION

The solanum lycocarpum is known as wolf apple, because maned wolf's feed these apples to cure its health problems. It is perennial plant, but in rainy season the flowering intensity is high. The trees grow up to 3-5 m height. It has thorn on branches. The leaves and stem have white hairs on outer surface. The fruit diameter is varying from 8-13 cm. The mass of fruit is vary from 400-900g.[2]

Kingdom: plantae

Order: solanales

Family: Solanaceae

Genus: Solanum

Species: lycocarpum

The fruit contains 1.5% of glycoalkaloids, when it is dry. The unripe fruit is rich in tannin. The tannin has enormous benefits. It decreases the blood urea nitrogen content, inhibition of lipid per oxidation, lipolysis in fat cell, anticarcinogenic, antiseptic. It is also good food preservative.[1]

The ripe fruit contain enormous amount of moisture content, few amounts of protein and fiber. It also contains ethyl butanoate so; it has apple smell. The cow and other butter consist of high amount of cholesterol. So, it cannot include in our daily diet. Instead of cow butter we include wolf apple butter. Because it has the ability to reduce the cholesterol in our body.

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Take 1 kg of wolf apple (900g ripe;100g unripe). Take the seeds and peel away. Wash it clearly. Cut the wolf apple into small pieces. Add little amount of water and grind it well. Filter and take the extract. Add the extract in three vessel separately. Add cane sugar in one vessel and another two is added with White sugar and jaggery separately.

The agar agar is completely dissolving in hot water and add to three vessels. Stir the mixture well. Keep the vessels on the stove and boil at the medium flame between 70-75°C. Turn off the stove, if the mixture gets well cooked. Finally add little amount of organic food red color which is extract from beetroot. Keep it in room temperature until it cool. No need of add preservative because tannin itself act as natural preservative. Pour the mixture in three glass container and store in refrigerator.

Fig.1

III. QUALITY ANALYSIS

1)Sheet test:

In sheet test, the butter from three glass container is taken in three different clean spoon and it is slowly drops in the sheet to check the consistency of the product. It slowly drops because of the addition of agar agar. The agar agar increase the viscosity of butter. It also protect the quality of butter.[4]

2)Drop test:

A small amount from three butter sample is drop into water in the vessel. It is not mixed with water. So, it is better in consistency.[9]

3)Refrigerator testing:

In refrigerator test, the small amount of fruit butter is taken in plate and keep it freeze for sometimes. And then remove the butter if it is easily to remove then it is better in quality.[7]

4)Sugar tests:

The brix valve is divided by two, we can get the value of total sucrose in the product. Its unit is brix.[5]

5)carbohydrate test:

DNS method is used to determine the carbohydrate in the samples. The alkaline solution of 3,5-dinitro salicylic acid react with reducing sugar and convert into 3-amino 5-

nitrosalicyclic acid. The solution is turned into orange colour that indicates the presence of reducing sugar. Reagent involved in DNS method are glucose working standard 10mg/10ml, DNS reagent (3ml) and 40% potassium sodium tartarate.[8]

6) Protein test:

Lowry's method is used to determine the protein content in wolf apple. Copper is mainly present in Lowry's reagent and it can react with peptide bond present in protein. Then the copper is reduced to blue colour to indicate the presence of Protein reagent are A-2% sodium carbonate in 0.1N, sodium hydroxide reagent B-0.5%, cupric sulphate in 1%, potassium tartarate, reagent C-1 and reagent B is added to 50 ml of reagent A and BSA standard-1mg/ml[6]

IV. SENSORY ANALYSIS

1) smell test: The wolf apple contains ethyl butanoate. Therefore, the butter has smell of apple.

2) colour test: It is bright red in colour because of the addition of organic beetroot extract.

3) Texture test: By addition of agar agar it is mucilaginous in texture. so it is easily to have with bread or rotties.

Result and discussion:

The amount of carbohydrate, protein and sugar are mentioned in the table 1. The white sugar is rich in taste but it has more chemical substance. So it is not good for health. It causes diseases like gum bleeding, diabetes, obesity etc... The jaggery and cane sugar is quite less in taste but it is good for health.

Table 1 consists of quality analysis of solanum lycocarpum

S.no	Quality analysis	Result
1.	Carbohydrate	11%
2.	Protein	1.5%
3.	Sugar	20.3%

CONCLUSION

The wolf apple butter control cholesterol in our body. so we can overcome the diseases like diabetes, hypertension, blood pressure, obesity etc... The natural sweeter like Jaggery and cane sugar and the artificial sweeter sugar is added in separate sample. The natural sweeter is more effective than artificial sweeter. So we must include jaggery and cane sugar in the preparation of butter.

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